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SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL BASIS OF EMOTIONAL
INTELLIGENCE IN STUDENTS

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Annotation. In the current era, the formation of a positive attitude towards fundamental changes aimed at the political, socio-economic and cultural-spiritual development of the country through the study of the psychological aspects of students' skills and abilities to achieve intellectual potential is of urgent socio-psychological importance. A person's emotional abilities, as a result of their management by their intellect, lead to the achievement of efficiency in personal and professional activities. In this article, we will shed light on the emotional intelligence of students.

Keywords: emotional intelligence, personality, student, professional activity, phenomenon of intellect.

Аннотация. В современную эпоху актуальное социально-психологическое значение приобретает формирование позитивного отношения к кардинальным изменениям, направленным на политическое, социально-экономическое и культурно-духовное развитие страны посредством изучения психологических аспектов способностей и возможностей учащихся к раскрытию интеллектуального потенциала. Эмоциональные способности человека, управляемые его интеллектом, приводят к успеху в личной и профессиональной деятельности. В этой статье мы прольем свет на эмоциональный интеллект студентов.

Ключевые слова: эмоциональный интеллект, личность, студент, профессиональная деятельность, интеллектуальный феномен.

Anotatsiya. Hozirgi davrda talabalarning intellektual salohiyatga erishish ko'nikma va malakalarini psixologik jihatlarini tadqiq etish orqali mamlakatni siyosiy, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy va madaniy-ma'naviy rivojlantirishga qaratilgan tub o'zgarishlarga

ijobiy daxldorlik munosabatni shakllantirish dolzarb ijtimoiy-psixologik ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shaxsning emotsional qobiliyatlari, uning intellekti bilan boshqarishlihi natijasida shaxsiy va kasbiy faoliyatda samaradorlikka erishishga sabab bo‘ladi. Ushbu maqolada talabalarning emotsional intellekti haqida yoritib beramiz.

Kalit so‘zlar: emotsional intellekt, shaxs, talaba, kasbiy faoliyat, intellekt fenomeni.

Introduction. Given the increasing need for human capital, the struggle for consciousness, intellect, and abilities in the process of globalization, the extent to which the work of identifying the structural qualities of the priority psychological determinants of the professional development of a given student is responsible in many cases depends on our knowledge of the psychological factor of emotional intelligence and its components.

Today, it is possible to separately note scientific studies that demonstrate the necessity of the problem of emotional intelligence in the world of science and the development of society and substantiate its methodological roots.

Discussion. First of all, there is a unique approach to understanding the essence of the concept of emotional intelligence, in which it is important to take into account the evolution of the application of this phenomenon.

Emotional intelligence - the issue of determining the psychological significance of a student's professional development and drawing scientific conclusions is considered one of the main problems of psychological disciplines. Therefore, it is impossible to discuss the issue of forming and developing the psychological significance of a student's professional development without somehow assessing the scope of theoretical, scientific and practical, methodological research on emotional intelligence.

Moreover, all researchers, while applying the methodological principles of psychology, theoretically and scientifically substantiate one or another aspect of emotional intelligence. In this work, it is possible to cite several psychological approaches aimed at identifying psychological tasks that are of significant theoretical and scientific importance for emotional intelligence.

Literature review. The concept of emotional intelligence was first introduced into science on a scientific basis by researchers D. Meyer and P. Solovey. According to them, emotional intelligence is the process of expressing, understanding, organizing, managing, and assimilating thoughts and feelings [1]. Later, researcher D. Goleman published his book “Emotional Intelligence”, which laid the foundation for a new direction in the study of emotional intelligence in psychology. In his work, the author described the inextricable link between emotional intelligence and the cerebral

hemispheres and the Mendelian zone as follows: "The information about our emotions, which is processed in the cerebral hemispheres, is of an unconscious nature and is understood only after it is processed. Our ability to understand and manage the emotional states of other people is not emotional intelligence, but should be explained in terms of emotional competence." The content of emotional competence includes emotional self-awareness, self-management, understanding and management of social relationships"[4]. Thus, emotional competence provides in its content the ability to manage and understand emotions, regulate emotions in social relationships. In addition, according to D. Gouleman, intelligence and emotional intelligence are distinct, non-contradictory concepts. And emotional intelligence includes in its content the following psychological includes the following components[3]:

- Self-awareness;
- Self-management;
- Quick understanding of social situations;
- Management of interpersonal relationships, effective communication style.

In contrast to the above considerations, researchers R.D. Roberts, J. Matthews, M.R. Seidner and D.V. Lucin put forward their own approach to the problem of emotional intelligence. That is, according to the views of these researchers, emotional intelligence is a combination of "cognitive" and "personality" qualities. is a complex mental process consisting of [96]. These two important elements, which illuminate emotional intelligence, are explained through cognitive, motivational, and personality models [2].

Therefore, we also join R. Bar-On's theory of the formation and development of emotional intelligence through cognition, because the basic criteria of emotional intelligence are mastered by the individual in the activities he performs throughout his life, including communication, play, study, and labor activity [5].

Result and analysis. According to the research of the Russian psychologist D.V. Lyusin, who conducted extensive research on the phenomenon of emotional intelligence, there are two aspects inherent in emotional intelligence, namely "business personality" and "interpersonal" relationships. According to his theory, emotional intelligence should be explained through the following [4]:

- understanding emotions, or the ability to understand the language of one's own or other people's emotional feelings;
- identifying emotions, or the ability to distinguish, isolate, and correctly use them in the right places;
- the ability to distinguish between the causes and consequences that cause emotional states;

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- the ability to sufficiently slow down intense emotions, control the intensity of feelings;
- easy understanding of expressive expressions;
- the experience of being able to evoke one or another emotion in one's activities and relationships.

These may not be factors that determine labor productivity. However, they are considered systems that ensure success in activities.

Emotional intelligence is interconnected with and builds on emotional competence. A certain level of emotional intelligence is necessary for the development of specific competencies related to emotions. For example, the ability to recognize a person's emotions gives a wide opportunity to develop such abilities as understanding and encouraging and influencing others' emotions.

V.S. Yurkevich, based on his own research and that of other researchers, argues that those who are 95% intellectually competent may have more difficulty in developing emotional intelligence [4]. The author also studies the issue of "infantile emotional relationships" in children, recognizing it as a loss of interest in activities not related to learning and difficulties in interacting with peers.

Conclusion. The development of emotional intelligence begins in childhood and its formation is inextricably linked to the family upbringing environment. That is, the tendency of parents to rationally resolve interpersonal and interpersonal relationships, later, helps the child to better understand his own emotions, and develop such determinants of emotional intelligence at a high level.

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